

REINFORCING

News Release: REINFORCING Launches ORRI Platform to Advance Open and Responsible Research and Innovation Across Europe

4 November 2024 – The REINFORCING project is pleased to announce the launch of its Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) Platform, an online central hub of knowledge and expertise that provides resources for both newcomers and experienced organizations on their ORRI journey.

The [ORRI Platform](#) features seven open calls for financial support, offering grants to new and seasoned organizations implementing ORRI. These grants are designed to fund projects that promote openness and responsibility in research and innovation, equipping organizations with essential resources to succeed.

Beyond funding, the platform offers a suite of services including resources that can help users in their journey towards ORRI. Tools, best practices, actionable strategies are curated and organized to drive effective outcomes.

The ORRI Platform fosters community engagement by connecting a vibrant network of organizations and territories who are advancing or would like to embark on ORRI. The community provides opportunities to share insights, exchange best practices, and build impactful partnerships across Europe. A virtual ORRI Map further enhances this engagement, helping users connect with experienced entities that could support on their ORRI practices.

To address specific challenges, the ORRI Platform will soon introduce expert-led training sessions and tailored pathways, guiding users step-by-step toward effective ORRI solutions. These upcoming features will help organizations overcome barriers and advance in their ORRI practices.

Funded under the Horizon Europe R&I Framework Programme, REINFORCING is a 50-month EU initiative aimed at mainstreaming ORRI across Europe.

MORE INFORMATION

<https://reinforcing.eu/>

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